

Appendix A. Lemmas

Lemma A.1. *Let the function E_t be defined according to equation 1. Then*

$$\frac{\partial E_t}{\partial w_{tij}} = -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj})f'(a_{tj})x_{ti}.$$

PROOF

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_t}{\partial w_{tij}} &= \frac{\partial(\sum_j \frac{1}{2}(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj})^2)}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{definition of } E_t \\ &= \frac{\partial(\frac{1}{2}(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj})^2)}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{error for neuron } j \\ &= \frac{\partial(\frac{1}{2}(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj})^2)}{\partial \hat{y}_{tj}} \frac{\partial \hat{y}_{tj}}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{chain rule} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) \frac{\partial \hat{y}_{tj}}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{partial derivative} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) \frac{\partial \hat{y}_{tj}}{\partial a_{tj}} \frac{\partial a_{tj}}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{chain rule} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) \frac{\partial f(a_{tj})}{\partial a_{tj}} \frac{\partial a_{tj}}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{definition of } \hat{y}_{tj} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{tj}) \frac{\partial a_{tj}}{\partial w_{tij}} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{tj}) \frac{\partial(\sum_k x_{tk} w_{tkj})}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{definition of } a_{tj} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{tj}) \sum_k \frac{\partial(x_{tk} w_{tkj})}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{properties of summation} \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{tj}) \frac{\partial(x_{ti} w_{tij})}{\partial w_{tij}} && \text{zero for all } k \neq i \\ &= -(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{tj}) x_{ti}. && \text{partial derivative} \end{aligned}$$

Lemma A.2. *Using the variables defined in section 2.2, let $\mathbf{x}_t \in \{0, 1\}^m$, $\mathbf{y}_t \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Let f be the identity function for all o_j . Let $\eta = \alpha\beta$. Then, the learning rule of Rescorla-Wagner can be written as the following*

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta w_{tij} &= \eta(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) f'(a_{ti}) x_{ti} && \text{Equation 2} \\
&= \eta(y_{tj} - \hat{y}_{tj}) \frac{\partial a_{ti}}{\partial a_{ti}} x_{ti} && \text{identity function} \\
&= \eta(y_{tj} - \sum_i x_{ti} w_{tij}) x_{ti}. && \text{definition of } \hat{y}_{tj} \\
&= \begin{cases} \eta(y_{tj} - \sum_i x_{ti} w_{tij}), & \text{if } x_{ti} = 1; \\ 0, & \text{if } x_{ti} = 0. \end{cases} && x_{ti} \text{ is binary} \\
&= \begin{cases} \eta(1 - \sum_i x_{ti} w_{tij}), & \text{if } x_{ti} = 1 \text{ and } y_{tj} = 1; \\ \eta(0 - \sum_i x_{ti} w_{tij}), & \text{if } x_{ti} = 1 \text{ and } y_{tj} = 0; \\ 0, & \text{if } x_{ti} = 0. \end{cases} && y_{tj} \text{ is binary}
\end{aligned}$$

Lemma A.3. Let $\mathbf{X}$, $\mathbf{Y}$, and $\mathbf{W}$ be three matrices such that $\mathbf{XW} = \mathbf{Y}$, and let $\mathbf{X}$ be an m -by- m invertible matrix. Then $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{Y}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{XW} &= \mathbf{Y} \\
\mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{XW} &= \mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{Y} && \text{left multiply both sides with } \mathbf{X}^{-1} \\
\mathbf{I}_m\mathbf{W} &= \mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{Y} && \mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{I}_m \\
\mathbf{W} &= \mathbf{X}^{-1}\mathbf{Y} && \mathbf{I}_m\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix B. Data

Some of the imperfect alignments by the forced aligner are visualized in Figure B1 and Figure B2.

Appendix C. Auditory features

C.1. Summary of algorithms

Figure C1 and Figure C2 illustrate the auditory processing by the FBS and the C-FBS procedures, respectively, for one auditory rendition of the word *between*. The observed improvement in the granularity of C-FBS features arise from using 1) different windowing functions in envelope smoothing, 2) different methods for the convolution of the envelope and the windowing function for smoothing, and 3) different choice of the extrema – minima in FBS versus maxima in C-FBS algorithm. The average number of chunks ($N = 131371$) is significantly greater in C-FBS chunks split according to maxima ($M = 2.23$, $SD = 1.07$) compared to C-FBS chunks split based on minima ($M = 1.98$, $SD = 1.05$) of the envelope ($W = 1726912218.5$, $p < 0.0001$).

Figure B1. Waveform and Hilbert envelope (in orange) for 4 misaligned words that are too short.

Figure B2. Waveform and Hilbert envelope (in orange) for 4 words with imperfect alignments. There is a piece of silence or breathing sound present in the beginning of the signal for each word.

Figure C1. Auditory processing by the FBS algorithm for one auditory rendition of the word *between*. The first panel depicts the waveform, along with the Hilbert envelope and the chunk boundary found by the FBS chunking procedure. The panel in the middle, which is aligned with the top panel in time, shows the normalized discretized log MEL energies at different frequency bands. Possible values are integer numbers between 0 and 5. Below that, an FBS feature is presented as an example in magenta that summarizes the energy values in the seventeenth frequency band of the first chunk. Conceptually, this feature represents one dimension of the FBS feature vectors. The value of the feature vector at this dimension is toggled from 0 to 1, indicating that the mentioned feature is present in the current audio token. For our dataset, the FBS vectors have a dimensionality of 40578. [Click here](#) or scan QR code to listen.

Figure C2. Auditory processing by the C-FBS algorithm for the same auditory rendition of the word *between* in Figure C1. The first panel depicts the waveform, along with the Hilbert envelope and the chunk boundary found by the C-FBS chunking procedure. The panel in the middle, which is aligned with the top panel in time, shows the log MEL energies at different frequency bands. Possible values are real numbers less than 0. Take the seventeenth band of the first chunk, framed in magenta, as an example. From the list of energy values, an order-preserving random sample of length 20 is taken and added to the C-FBS vector. In addition to the selected values, the frequency band number, and the correlation of this band with the following bands in the chunk are also appended to the vector. For our dataset, the C-FBS vectors have a dimensionality of 6510.

C.2. C-FBS neighborhood

As an initial step in investigating the neighborhood structure of the features, we looked at the top 9 nearest C-FBS feature vectors for some example words. Here we present the plots for the target words *president*, *price*, *capital*, and *soccer* in Figure C3. Similarly sounding words to the target words appear in the list of top 9 nearest neighbors of the target words' C-FBS vectors. It can be observed from the lowest subpanel of the top right panel that, for a particular audio rendition of the target word *price*, 2 other audio tokens of the same word and similarly sounding words such as *place* appear among the top 9 neighbors.

Appendix D. Semantic vectors

Addition of a small amount of Gaussian noise brought about better statistical properties for the TASA2 vectors, making them less dependent on outliers. Figure D1 illustrates that the distribution of vector values is closer to the normal distribution after addition of noise. The first panel, as an example, shows the histogram for the values in the semantic vector of the word *away* before and after addition of noise. The remaining panels show the distribution of different statistical properties for all of the 23 561 vectors in the TASA2 space. Addition of noise decreases the skewness of vectors from an average of 12.19 to 0.61 (third panel) and kurtosis from an average of 322.89 to 18.27 (fourth panel) while keeping the mean of vectors exactly at an average of -2×10^{-6} (second panel).

Figure C3. Neighborhood structure of C-FBS features for four target words *president* (the top left panel), *price* (the top right panel), *capital* (the bottom left panel), and *soccer* (the bottom right panel). Each of the 4 subpanels in the four panels belongs to a different audio rendition of the corresponding target word. The x-axis represents the Euclidean distance between the feature vectors of the target audio token and the audio token of words listed on the y-axis. In all subplots, the first nearest neighbor belongs to the target audio token itself (with a distance of zero) and is, therefore, not shown. The second nearest neighbor (with smallest distance) to the ninth nearest neighbor (with largest distance) are ordered from bottom to top on the y-axis.

Figure D1. Histograms visualizing the distribution of different statistical properties for the TASA2 vectors, before and after addition of a small amount of Gaussian noise. Top left panel: distribution of values in the semantic vector for the word *away* is closer to the normal distribution after addition of noise. The remaining panels belong to the distribution of mean, skewness, and kurtosis of all TASA2 vectors ($N = 23\,561$).